

Patient: **PSAM 8MOIS HE 4066 PHOTOPIC FLICKER, CATHY, 31/08/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 00:41:26
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1	50,9	115µV
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1		
2 L-2	50,9	124µV
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2		

Patient: **PSAM 8MOIS HE 4066 PHOTOPIC FLICKER, CATHY, 31/08/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 00:41:26
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1		
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1	50,9	52,9µV
2 L-2		
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2	51,9	54,3µV

Patient: **PSAM 8MOIS HE 4066 PHOTOPIC, CATHY, 31/08/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 00:22:24
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic single flash 2

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
3 R-1	18,6	51,4	29,7µV	81,9µV
5 R-1	23,5	54,3	35,6µV	156µV
2 L-2				
4 L-2	26,4	54,8	25,9µV	72,5µV
6 L-2	25,9	55,8	33,4µV	146µV

Patient: **PSAM 8MOIS HE 4066 SCOTOPIC, CATHY, 31/08/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 00:09:33
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
scotopic single flash 3

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
2 L-2				
3 R-1				
4 L-2				
5 R-1	22,7	54,0	59,7µV	175µV
6 L-2	20,4	50,9	71,6µV	150µV

Patient: **PSAM 7MOIS HE 4088 PHOTOPIC FLICKER, CATHY, 22/09/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 03:10:23
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1	45,0	231µV
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1		
2 L-2	46,0	220µV
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2		

Patient: **PSAM 7MOIS HE 4088 PHOTOPIC FLICKER, CATHY, 22/09/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 03:10:23
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1		
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1	46,0	159µV
2 L-2		
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2	47,9	119µV

Patient: **PSAM 7MOIS HE 4088 PHOTOPIC, CATHY, 22/09/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 02:54:43
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic single flash 2

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
3 R-1	20,1	45,0	20,5µV	172µV
5 R-1	16,1	51,4	38,9µV	177µV
2 L-2				
4 L-2	22,5	47,5	20,3µV	153µV
6 L-2	21,5	49,9	58,2µV	248µV

Patient: **PSAM 7MOIS HE 4088 SCOTOPIC, CATHY, 22/09/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 02:39:46
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
scotopic single flash 3

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
2 L-2				
3 R-1				
4 L-2				
5 R-1	12,5	47,7	139µV	209µV
6 L-2	17,2	48,5	75,2µV	246µV

Patient: **PSAM 8MOIS HE 4155 PHOTOPIC FLICKER, CATHY, 05/09/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 01:14:30
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1	47,0	77,5µV
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1		
2 L-2	47,9	203µV
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2		

Patient: **PSAM 8MOIS HE 4155 PHOTOPIC FLICKER, CATHY, 05/09/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 01:14:30
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1		
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1	47,0	39,0µV
2 L-2		
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2	48,9	138µV

Patient: **PSAM 8MOIS HE 4155 PHOTOPIC, CATHY, 05/09/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 00:57:42
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic single flash 2

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
3 R-1	23,0	58,7	7,57µV	76,0µV
5 R-1	20,1	52,8	18,4µV	96,9µV
2 L-2				
4 L-2	23,0	48,4	19,4µV	157µV
6 L-2	21,0	54,8	36,7µV	190µV

Patient: **PSAM 8MOIS HE 4155 SCOTOPIC, CATHY, 05/09/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 00:43:15
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Diagnosis:
scotopic single flash 3

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
2 L-2				
3 R-1				
4 L-2				
5 R-1	10,2	55,6	66,1µV	158µV
6 L-2	13,3	57,1	105µV	200µV

Patient: **PSAM 8MOIS HE 4156 PHOTOPIC FLICKER, CATHY, 31/08/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 01:42:32
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1	57,7	31,4µV
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1		
2 L-2	61,6	35,1µV
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2		

Patient: **PSAM 8MOIS HE 4156 PHOTOPIC FLICKER, CATHY, 31/08/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 01:42:32
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1		
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1	46,0	13,4µV
2 L-2		
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2	53,8	11,5µV

Patient: **PSAM 8MOIS HE 4156 PHOTOPIC, CATHY, 31/08/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 01:25:41
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic single flash 2

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
3 R-1	25,9	59,2	29,3µV	43,8µV
5 R-1	23,0	53,3	16,3µV	49,7µV
2 L-2				
4 L-2	28,4	57,2	6,16µV	14,3µV
6 L-2	25,9	52,8	18,7µV	51,0µV

Patient: **PSAM 8MOIS HE 4156 SCOTOPIC, CATHY, 31/08/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 01:16:41
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
scotopic single flash 3

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
2 L-2				
3 R-1				
4 L-2				
5 R-1	25,8	56,4	33,8µV	79,0µV
6 L-2	22,7	54,0	26,9µV	92,0µV

Patient: **PSAM 8MOIS HE 4188 PHOTOPIC FLICKER, CATHY, 31/08/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 02:09:23
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1	65,6	60,0µV
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1		
2 L-2	48,9	51,2µV
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2		

Patient: **PSAM 8MOIS HE 4188 PHOTOPIC FLICKER, CATHY, 31/08/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 02:09:23
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1		
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1	51,9	14,4µV
2 L-2		
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2	47,0	19,8µV

Patient: **PSAM 8MOIS HE 4188 SPHOTOPIC, CATHY, 31/08/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 01:55:52
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic single flash 2

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
3 R-1	22,0	61,6	7,93µV	52,2µV
5 R-1	25,9	56,3	31,3µV	63,5µV
2 L-2				
4 L-2	20,5	64,6	10,6µV	50,0µV
6 L-2	23,0	53,3	28,0µV	86,0µV

Patient: **PSAM 8MOIS HE 4188 SCOTOPIC, CATHY, 31/08/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 01:44:31
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
scotopic single flash 3

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
2 L-2				
3 R-1				
4 L-2				
5 R-1	32,1	56,4	76,7µV	122µV
6 L-2	21,9	54,0	48,2µV	118µV

Patient: **PSAM 6 MOIS HE 4238 photopic flicker, cathy, 10/11/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 02:41:49
 ID:

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Diagnosis:
photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1	49,9	72,7µV
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1		
2 L-2	48,9	80,5µV
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2		

Patient: **PSAM 6 MOIS HE 4238 photopic flicker, cathy, 10/11/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 02:41:49
 ID:

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1		
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1	64,6	24,4µV
2 L-2		
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2	62,6	25,5µV

Patient: **PSAM 6 MOIS HE 4238 photopic, cathy, 10/11/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 02:26:38
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic single flash 2

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
3 R-1	23,5	55,8	19,7µV	70,6µV
5 R-1	25,0	54,3	33,1µV	150µV
2 L-2				
4 L-2	15,2	62,1	10,7µV	56,8µV
6 L-2	24,5	54,3	37,0µV	158µV

Patient: **PSAM 6 MOIS HE 4238 scotopic, cathy, 10/11/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 02:14:54
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
scotopic single flash 3

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
2 L-2				
3 R-1				
4 L-2				
5 R-1	19,6	54,0	43,8µV	147µV
6 L-2	22,7	54,0	51,6µV	160µV

Patient: **PSAM 6 MOIS HE 4239 photopic flicker, cathy, 10/11/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 02:12:49
 ID:

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Diagnosis:
photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1	58,7	65,5µV
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1		
2 L-2	64,6	33,7µV
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2		

Patient: **PSAM 6 MOIS HE 4239 photopic flicker, cathy, 10/11/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 02:12:49
 ID:

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1		
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1	47,0	22,5µV
2 L-2		
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2	50,9	8,45µV

Patient: **PSAM 6 MOIS HE 4239 photopic, cathy, 10/11/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 01:56:10
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic single flash 2

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
3 R-1	25,9	70,9	9,46µV	70,6µV
5 R-1	29,4	63,6	53,9µV	149µV
2 L-2				
4 L-2	24,5	64,1	793nV	42,2µV
6 L-2	28,4	60,7	19,7µV	49,6µV

Patient: **PSAM 6 MOIS HE 4239 scotopic, cathy, 10/11/2012**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 01:42:47
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
scotopic single flash 3

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
2 L-2				
3 R-1				
4 L-2				
5 R-1	25,8	62,6	48,4µV	133µV
6 L-2	36,0	60,3	25,6µV	73,9µV